

ISic3662

I.Sicily inscription 3662

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

funerary

Material

limestone (calcarenite gialla locale)

Object

block

Editor

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Lilybaeum

Place of origin (modern)

Marsala

Provenance

excavation 1987-1988, via De Gasperi, proprietà Acquiconsult, tombs
131/132

Coordinates

Current Location

Italy, Sicily, Marsala, Museo archeologico
regionale Lilibeo Marsala - Baglio Anselmi

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

Edition: EDR108328

1. [---] Λευκάδιος [---]

Apparatus

Translation

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

EDR 108328

Bibliography

Bechtold, B. 1999. La necropoli di Lilybaeum. Palermo. At 321 tav.40.382

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